

Acute kidney injury in neonates in a level - III NICU

Authors:

Dr. Rashida Arsiwala¹, Dr. Chhaya Valvi²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Paediatrics, Grant Government Medical College, Mumbai, India.

²Professor and UG vice dean, Department of Paediatrics, Grant Government Medical College, Mumbai, India.

Corresponding Author:

Dr. Rashida Arsiwala

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15315709>

Article Received: 19-March-2025, Revised: 09-April-2025, Accepted: 29-April-2025

ABSTRACT:

Background: Acute kidney injury (AKI) is a common occurrence in the NICU with a variable incidence of 6-24% globally and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality. The cause of AKI is multifactorial. The identification of the risk factors and avoidance of the exposure at the earliest followed by application of patient specific treatment strategies is aimed at improving outcomes of neonatal AKI. **Methods:** A cross sectional descriptive study was conducted in the NICU of B.J Government Medical College and Sassoon Hospital, Pune with 95 neonates to determine the risk factors and short-term outcomes of neonates admitted with Acute kidney injury (AKI). Data was collected in a paper based proforma and variables for this study were analysed. **Results:** AKI was seen more in preterm neonates less than 32 weeks of gestation (56.84%). Mortality with AKI is significantly associated with prematurity (p=0.0032). AKI was more in low birth weight neonates (87%). The mean birth weight of the babies who succumbed were significantly lower than those who survived (p=0.004). Significantly higher number of cases with no birth asphyxia survived (p=0.02). Babies having AKI who had no evidence of intraventricular haemorrhage or sepsis, absence of indwelling central catheters had a better survival, (p-0.003), (p-0.0000001) and (p-0.0007) respectively. Mortality was significantly reduced in babies with AKI in whom aminoglycosides were not used (p=0.0001). A significantly higher number of deaths were observed with AKI stage 3 (p=0.0000183). **Conclusion:** Prematurity, sepsis, birth asphyxia, low birth weight, presence of indwelling central catheters, intraventricular haemorrhage and use of aminoglycosides were identified as risk factors of neonatal AKI. Stage 1 was associated with prolonged duration of hospital stay and greater survival. Monitoring and timely intervention in neonates can prevent the progression and outcome of AKI and will thus decrease early mortality.

Keywords: Acute kidney injury, AKI, NICU

INTRODUCTION:

AKI is a common occurrence in the NICU and is associated with increased morbidity and mortality with available data showing variable incidence of AKI in neonatal population around the globe, ranging from 6-24 % [1,2] The cause of AKI is multifactorial, many patients having a mixed etiology where one or more risk factors coexist and complicate recognition and treatment. [3] 1 in 10 babies born worldwide are premature [4,5] causing various complications. AKI is a complication which occurs in 30% of all neonates, with almost 50% of those born <29 weeks GA affected [6].

The kidneys of neonates are particularly susceptible to hypoperfusion because of the physiologic characteristics of neonatal kidneys, high renal vascular resistance, high plasma renin activity, low glomerular filtration rate, decreased intercortical perfusion and decreased reabsorption of sodium in the proximal tubules in the first few days of a neonate. [7] Neonates

also have persistence of maternal creatinine and massive fluid shifts associated with post-natal weight loss affecting the intricate fluid electrolyte balance. [6] It has also been observed that those who develop neonatal AKI are at an increased risk for development of chronic kidney disease (CKD). [8]

The short-term outcome of therapy for AKI in neonates is highly dependent on the underlying etiology of AKI, dysfunction of organ systems and the facilities for renal replacement therapy. Non-dialytic management of AKI may restore appropriate renal function without exposure to complications often encountered with RRT apart from the technical difficulties [9] like small sizes of vessels, peritoneal space and expensive compared to adults [10]. Neonatal AKI represents a rapidly evolving area in clinical research with a lack of minimal evidence based studies hence this study was done to identify the risk factors and avoidance of the exposure at the earliest, application of patient specific treatment strategies to improve outcomes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a hospital based cross-sectional descriptive study done at level III NICU at tertiary care teaching hospital, B.J Government Medical College and Sassoon Hospital, Pune. Research proposal was approved by IEC BJMC.

Study population were all neonates admitted to NICU. The sample size was calculated using the formula: $N=4PQ/d^2$, where prevalence is 12 as per a pilot study conducted in the NICU, we took error as 7% hence sample size was 86. Assuming the probability of withdrawal of consents and deaths, an estimated 10% was added to the calculated sample size. Thus the final sample size was 95. Patients were studied from March 2021 to August 2022. Inclusion criteria were neonates from day 1 to day 28 of life with AKI. AKI is defined as any of the following (Not Graded) as per KDIGO classification: Increase in SCr by ≥ 0.3 mg/dL within 48 hours; or Increase in SCr to ≥ 1.5 times baseline, which is known or presumed to have occurred within the prior 7 days; or Urine volume < 0.5 ml/kg/h for 6 hours. [11] Exclusion Criteria were lethal chromosomal anomaly/ multiple lethal congenital anomalies, Antenatally diagnosed congenital

anomalies of kidney and urinary tract and Babies who expire within 48 hrs of admission.

Written informed consent of the parents was taken and cases studied. Urine output was measured every 6 hrs Sr Creatinine levels were done 12 hourly and maternal, perinatal and neonatal risk factors were assessed. Cases were managed according to the unit protocol. Follow up of cases was done till short term outcomes Discharge/ Discharge against Medical Advise/ Death. Neonates were categorised according to their stage of AKI [11] Stage 1- Serum creatinine 1.5–1.9 times baseline or ≥ 0.3 mg/dl increase or Urine output < 0.5 ml/kg/h for 6–12 hour; Stage 2- Serum creatinine 2.0–2.9 times baseline or < 0.5 ml/kg/h for ≥ 12 hours; Stage 3- Serum creatinine 3.0 times baseline or Increase in serum creatinine to ≥ 4.0 mg/dl or Initiation of renal replacement therapy or Urine output < 0.3 ml/kg/h for ≥ 24 hours or anuria for ≥ 12 hours. All maternal, perinatal and neonatal risk factors studied are mentioned in table 1. Data was collected in a paper based proforma all the variables for this study were analysed using Microsoft Office Excel 2016 & IBM SPSS Statistics' version 20.

Table no 1: Demographics, Maternal, Perinatal and Neonatal risk factors with AKI

Gender		
	N	%
Male	50	52.63
Female	45	47.37
Gestational age		
<32 weeks	54	56.84
>32 weeks	41	43.16
Birth weight		
	N	%
<1	22	23.16
1-1.5	29	30.53
1.5-2.5	32	33.68
>2.5	12	12.63
Maternal risk factors with AKI		
Risk factor	Present	
	N	%
Antenatal steroids	27	28.42
Oligohydramnios	17	17.89
Preeclampsia	10	10.52
Antepartum hemorrhage	8	8.42
Polyhydramnios	5	5.27
Chronic hypertension	4	4.22
Gestational diabetes	3	3.13
Maternal hypothyroidism	3	3.13
Eclampsia	3	3.13
Perinatal Risk Factors and AKI		
Risk factor	Present	
	N	%
Birth asphyxia	12	12.5
Meconium aspiration syndrome	5	5.2
Shoulder dystocia	3	3.13
Neonatal Risk factors and AKI		

Risk factor	Present	
Sepsis	47	49.47
Aminoglycosides	33	34.74
Indwelling central catheters	18	18.95
NSAIDS	8	8.42
Seizures	7	7.37
Intraventricular hemorrhage	6	6.31
Intrauterine growth retardation	6	6.31
Meningitis	3	3.16
Urinary tract infection	2	2.11
Diuretics	2	2.11
Vasopressors	2	2.11
Necrotizing enterocolitis	2	2.11

Table 02: Correlation of maternal, perinatal, and neonatal risk factors with severity of AKI

	MILD	MODERATE TO SEVERE	Total	P Value
OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS				
ABSENT	30(38.46%)	48(61.54%)	78(82.11%)	1
PRESENT	6(35.29%)	11(64.71%)	17(17.89%)	
BIRTH ASPHYXIA				
ABSENT	34(40.96%)	49(59.04%)	83(87.37%)	0.12
PRESENT	2(16.67%)	10(83.33%)	12(12.63%)	
SEPSIS				
ABSENT	24(48%)	26(52%)	50(52.63%)	0.03
PRESENT	12(26.67%)	33(73.33%)	45(47.37%)	
INDWELLING CENTRAL CATHETERS				
ABSENT	32(40%)	48(60%)	80(84.21%)	0.395
PRESENT	4(26.67%)	11(73.33%)	15(15.79%)	
INTRAVENTRICULAR HAEMORRHAGE				
ABSENT	36(40.45%)	53(59.55%)	89(93.96%)	0.7
PRESENT	0(0%)	6(100%)	6(6.32%)	
INTRAUTERINE GROWTH RETARDATION				
ABSENT	35(39.77%)	53(60.23%)	88(92.63%)	0.2471
PRESENT	1(14.29%)	6(85.17%)	7(7.37%)	
MENINGITIS				
ABSENT	33(36.67%)	58(63.33%)	91(95.79%)	0.22
PRESENT	3(75%)	1(25%)	4(4.21%)	
URINARYTRACTINFECTION				
ABSENT	35(37.63%)	58(62.37%)	93(97.89%)	0.61
PRESENT	1(50%)	1(50%)	2(2.11%)	
NECROTISING ENTEROCOLITIS				
ABSENT	35(37.63%)	58(62.37%)	93(97.89%)	0.72
PRESENT	1(50%)	1(50%)	2(2.11%)	

Table 03: Comparison of maternal, Perinatal, and Neonatal risk factors with mortality

	Death		Survived	
OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS				
ABSENT	34	43.59	44	56.14
PRESENT	7	41.18	10	58.82
BIRTH ASPHYXIA				
ABSENT	32	38.55	51	61.45
PRESENT	9	75	3	25
SEPSIS				

ABSENT	8	16.67	40	83.33
PRESENT	33	70.21	14	29.79
MENINGITIS				
ABSENT	40	43.96	51	56.04
PRESENT	1	25	3	75
URINARY TRACT INFECTION				
ABSENT	40	43.01	53	56.99
PRESENT	1	50	1	50
INDWELLING CENTRAL CATHETERS				
ABSENT	28	35.44	51	64.56
PRESENT	13	81.25	3	18.75
INTRAVENTRICULAR HAEMORRHAGE				
ABSENT	35	39.33	54	60.67
PRESENT	6	100	0	0
SEIZURES				
ABSENT	36	40.91	52	59.09
PRESENT	5	71.43	2	28.57

Significant association of survived with no asphyxic insult at birth ($p=0.02$), no IVH ($p=0.003$), absence of sepsis ($p=0.000001$) and in which central catheters were not inserted was seen. ($p=0.0007$)

Table 04: Outcome of AKI with AKI staging:

Stage of AKI	DAMA		Death		Discharge		Total	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
1	5	13.89	3	8.33	28	77.77	36	37.89
2	4	13.79	18	62.07	7	24.14	29	30.53
3	0	0	20	66.67	10	33.33	30	31.58
Total	9	9.47	41	43.16	45	47.37	95	100

AKI was associated with prematurity and low birth weight. Significantly higher number of cases with no birth asphyxia survived. An association between maternal factors studied and severity of AKI and mortality was not significant. Babies having AKI who had no evidence of intraventricular haemorrhage or sepsis, absence of indwelling central catheters had a better survival. Less mortality was seen in babies with AKI in whom aminoglycosides were not used. Mortality was greater in babies who required mechanical ventilation ($p = 0.00001$). Mean time (SD) of the onset of AKI was 5.69 days.

A significantly higher number of deaths was observed with AKI stage 3 ($p=0.0000183$). Those babies who had an early onset of AKI, were discharged in majority ($p=0.02$). The presence of AKI prolonged the mean duration of hospital stay significantly ($p=0.02$). The mean length of stay in hospital was highest with Stage 1 as compared to Stage 2 and Stage 3. ($p=0.00043$) The mean of Sr Creatinine at outcome was significantly highest at stage 3 as compared to stage 2 ($p=0.01896$).

DISCUSSION: The research in order to identify risk factors of AKI in neonates suggests sepsis, shock, birth asphyxia, intraventricular haemorrhage, use of aminoglycosides and central lines responsible. AKI was more associated with male gender but there was no association of gender with the severity. Our study reports increased incidence of AKI in low-birth-weight neonates (87.37%) which is in agreement with Coleman et al, 2022. [12] i.e AKI present in 60.2% low

birth weight neonates.. The mean birth weight in babies who died and those who survived are 1.18kg and 1.76kg respectively. The mean birth weight of the babies who died were significantly lower than those who survived. ($p = 0.004$). In the present study, most of the babies with AKI were less than 32 weeks of gestation at the time of delivery (87.37%). The cut off 32 weeks is taken as the feeding practices change around this time in babies according to the recommendations apart from the kidney maturation and fluid management. The mean gestational age of babies who died and those who survived were 31.21 and 34.02 respectively. In our study, the mean gestational age of babies who died were significantly less than those who survived ($p = 0.00032$). Infants with AKI had higher mortality before the PMA of 36 weeks ($p = 0.027$) according to study by Chien-Chung Lee et al 2017 [13]. This might be due to the fact that renal morphogenesis is completed by 36 weeks of gestation and premature babies continue to form nephrons even after birth but as they are exposed to ex utero risk factors of AKI, morphogenesis may be hampered.

In the current study, several maternal risk factors are taken into consideration, as significance with development of AKI was not observed. This may be due to our main limitation of small number of cases. In our study, among the perinatal risk factors studied, significantly higher number of cases with no birth asphyxia survived ($p = 0.02$), a finding which is

similar to the prevalence and mortality in AKI due to birth asphyxia in study by Momtaz et al 2014. [14] Renal involvement is frequent in neonates with birth asphyxia, which correlates with the severity of neurological damage and may lead to Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy, the serum creatinine level should thus be monitored daily in severely asphyxiated neonates as urine output is usually normal in such cases, thus included into study through KDIGO classification modified for neonates.

Significant association of survival of neonates with AKI with no IVH ($p=0.003$), absence of sepsis ($p=0.0000001$) and in neonates with no central catheters was obtained ($p=0.0007$). In a study by N Nandhagopal et al., 2020, [15] neonatal risk factors which were found to be associated with the development of AKI in the neonates are sepsis, shock, and birth asphyxia on univariate as well as logistic regression analysis (0.001, 0.001 and 0.001) respectively. On the contrary, in comparison with early outcomes, according to study by Momtaz et al 2014 [14], sepsis is not significantly contributing to mortality ($p=0.46$). In our study, babies in which Aminoglycosides were not used were significantly associated with survival ($p=0.0001$). This might be due to delay in recognition of AKI in an earlier stage and focuses on the importance of timely renal modification of nephrotoxic medication doses. Significantly higher number of deaths was observed with AKI stage 3. (Chi square-32.094, df-4, $p=0.0000183$), indicating earlier interventions in Stage 1 and 2 can prevent mortality. Mean length of stay in hospital was highest with Stage 1 as compared to Stage 2 and Stage 3. ($p = 0.00043$) The babies who were classified as Stage 1 of AKI required longer durations of intervention and eventually evaded mortality hence longer stay in the hospital. Studies which compare length of stay in newborns compared with stage of AKI have not been found to the best of our knowledge. Strengths- The study was conducted in a tertiary care teaching hospital where a greater number of deliveries were conducted. The high number of deliveries conducted resulted in a greater number of neonates with AKI being included in the study population. A higher referral for intensive care management of neonate was also observed. Limitations- The study population was small. A plan to study eGFR of neonates associated with AKI could not be executed, it shall be published in a subsequent study.

CONCLUSION:

We conclude that the prevalence of AKI in at-risk neonates is high, associated with significant mortality. This study contributes to the few Indian studies based on neonates with AKI to identify risk factors and study their outcomes after onset. Sepsis, birth asphyxia, prematurity, low birth weight, presence of indwelling central catheters, intraventricular haemorrhage and use of aminoglycosides are the main risk factors of neonatal AKI. Monitoring and timely intervention in

neonates with AKI can prevent morbidity and mortality.

REFERENCES:

1. Gouyon JB, Guignard JP. Management of acute renal failure in newborns. *Pediatr Nephrol.* (2000) 14:1037–44. Doi: 10.1007/s004670050068
2. Drukker A, Guignard JP. Renal aspects of the term and preterm infant: a selective update. *Curr Opin Pediatr.* (2002) 14:175–82. Doi: 10.1097/00008480-200204000-00006.
3. Cataldi L, Leone R, Moretti U, De Mitri B, Fanos V, Ruggeri L, et al. Potential risk factors for the development of acute renal failure in preterm newborn infants: a case- control study. *Arch Dis Child Fetal Neonatal Ed* 2005;90:F514e9. Sawant SP, Amin AS, Bhat M. Prevalence, pattern and outcome of congenital heart disease in Bhabha Atomic Research Centre Hospital, Mumbai. *The Indian Journal of Pediatrics.* 2013 Apr;80(4):286-91.
4. Cao, G.; Liu, J.; Liu, M. Global, Regional, and National Incidence and Mortality of Neonatal Preterm Birth, 1990–2019. *JAMA Pediatr* 2022, 176, 787–796.
5. Ohuma, E.O.; Moller, A.B.; Bradley, E.; Chakwera, S.; Hussain-Alkhateeb, L.; Lewin, A.; Okwaraji, Y.B.; Mahanani, W.R.; Johansson, E.B.; Lavin, T.; et al. National, regional, and worldwide estimates of preterm birth in 2020, with trends from 2010: A systematic analysis. *Lancet* 2023, 402, 1261–1271.
6. Jetton, J.G.; Boohaker, L.J.; Sethi, S.K.; Wazir, S.; Rohatgi, S.; Soranno, D.E.; Chishti, A.S.; Woroniecki, R.; Mammen, C.; Swanson, J.R.; et al. Incidence and outcomes of neonatal acute kidney injury (AWAKEN): A multicentre, multinational, observational cohort study. *Lancet Child Adolesc. Health* 2017, 1, 184–194.
7. Gharehbaghi MM, Peirovifor A. Evaluating causes of acute renal failure in newborn infants. *Pak J Med Sci.* 2007;23:877–80.
8. Alkandari O, Eddington KA, Hyder A, Gauvin F, Ducruet T, Gottesman R, et al. Acute kidney injury is an independent risk factor for pediatric intensive care unit mortality, longer length of stay and prolonged mechanical ventilation in critically ill children: a two-center retrospective cohort study. *Crit Care* 2011;15:R146. Khalil A, Aggarwal R, Thirupuram S, Arora R. Incidence of congenital heart disease among hospital live births

in India. *Indian pediatrics*. 1994 May 1;31(5):519-28.

9. Basu RK, Wheeler DS, Goldstein S, Doughty L. Acute renal replacement therapy in pediatrics. *Int J Nephrol*. 2011;2011:785392. Doi: 10.4061/2011/785392.

10. Lantos JD, Warady BA. The evolving ethics of infant dialysis. *Pediatr Nephrol*. 2013;28:1943–7. Doi: 10.1007/s00467-012-2351-1.

11. Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO) Acute Kidney Injury Work Group. KDIGO Clinical Practice Guideline for Acute Kidney Injury. *Kidney inter., Suppl*. 2012; 2: 1–138

12. Coleman C, Tambay Perez A, Selewski DT and Steflik HJ (2022) Neonatal Acute Kidney Injury. *Front. Pediatr*. 10:842544. Doi: 10.3389/fped.2022.842544

13. Lee C-C, Chan O-W, Lai M-Y, Hsu K-H, Wu T-W, Lim W-H, et al. (2017) Incidence and outcomes of acute kidney injury in extremely-low-birth-weight infants. *PLoS ONE* 12(11): e0187764. doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0187764

14. Momtaz et al., *J Clin Neonatol*. 2014 Apr-Jun; 3(2): 99–102. doi: [10.4103/2249-4847.134691](https://doi.org/10.4103/2249-4847.134691)

15. Nandhagopal N, Firdaus U, Ali SM, Afzal K. Incidence, risk factors, and outcome of acute kidney injury in hospitalized term newborns. *J Clin Neonatol* 2020;9:121-4